

A GUIDE OF HOW TO USE RESEARCH4LIFE

Access to the Unified Content Portal

- The Unified Content Portal and other portals are accessible through direct links:
 - Unified Portal - <https://portal.research4life.org/>
 - AGORA - <https://agora.research4life.org/>
 - ARDI - <https://ardi.research4life.org/>
 - **LOGIN** tab from the Research4Life initial page <https://www.research4life.org/>
- Any member of a registered institution can login to the portal using a **Username** and **Password**. Login details are usually available at the college Library.
- Access is available from desktop/laptop computers and mobile phones.

Initial Content Portal Pages (Note the symbol for login).

This presentation focuses on the Unified Content Portal but can also be used for AGORA or ARDI content portal training.

Welcome to Research4Life

 Share

Welcome to ARDI

 Share

Login to the Unified Content Portal

- You can login to the portal through the Research4life website:
<https://www.research4life.org/>
- Access to the login page is also located on the initial web pages of the five collections.
- In both cases, users will be prompted to enter login credentials.

Login instructions

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar containing the URL `login.research4life.org/tacgw/login.cshhtml`. The page header includes the `research4life` logo. The main content area has a blue background and a white login form titled "Secure Login". The form contains three input fields: "USER NAME" with a user icon, "PASSWORD" with a lock icon, and a dropdown menu currently set to "ENGLISH". A "LOGIN" button is positioned at the bottom right of the form.

- You must use the login credentials of their institution – both the username and password are case-sensitive & no spaces are allowed.
- Contact the institution's librarian for login info.

Initial display of the Unified Content Portal

- The initial page displays a link to the **Summon search box** that links to citations and full-text available at your institution.
- Click on the **person symbol** located at the top right corner of the login page to open the login information –in this case, for a Hinari Training: National Non-governmental login; the symbol has changed:
- Note that, after logging into the portal, you can ‘sign-in as a personal user’; see slides 29 & 30.

Hamburger Menu: Mobile phone access

- Displayed is the mobile phone version of the **Unified Content Portal**:
- Initial page; click on the **Hamburger Menu** symbol.
- The various browse and search and other content portal options are listed and will be discussed in subsequent slides.

Access to specific Collections from initial portal page

- Once logged in, scroll down the initial page till the **Collections** listing is displayed
- Note the links to the five collections.
- For Hinari, GOALI and OARE, the specific programmes and resources will be displayed from the Unified Content Portal.
- For AGORA and ARDI, the stand-alone content portals will be displayed. Click on **ARDI**.

portal.research4life.org

research4life

Welcome to Research4Life

Research4Life provides institutions in low-and middle-income countries with online access to academic and professional peer-reviewed content. We aim to improve teaching, research and policymaking in health, agriculture, the environment and other life, physical and social sciences.

👁 Collections

Research4Life content is grouped into the following collections:

- **Hinari** is one of the world's largest collections of **biomedical and health** literature.
- **AGORA** is an outstanding digital library collection in the fields of **food and agriculture**.
- **ARDI** gives access to **scientific and technical** information.
- **GOALI** focuses on **law and social sciences**, including politics, economics, philosophy, history and more.
- **OARE** collects information resources on **environment**, including ecology, geography, energy and more.

👁 Resources of the month

up to **100.000 RESOURCES**
NOW AVAILABLE THROUGH RESEARCH4LIFE

Browse **recent resources** to find content added in the last 30 days.

Browsing by Collections

- In the Unified Content Portal, the initial page displays the **Collections** option.
- Users can access the resources for a **specific collection** by clicking on the title of the program.
- The next slide displays the **AGORA** Collection within the Unified Content Portal.

ARDI Content Portal

- Displayed is the **ARDI** Content Portal.
- The features and browse/search options are similar to those in the Unified Content Portal
- To return to the Unified Content Portal, click on the **Research4Life logo**

ardi.research4life.org

ARDI
Research for Innovation

Content ▾ Help EN ▾

Welcome to ARDI

Search across all Research4Life...
Search function provided by Summon ADVANCED SEARCH

Welcome to ARDI

The Access to Research for Development and Innovation (ARDI) program, coordinated by WIPO together with its partners in the publishing industry, aims to increase the availability of scientific and technical information in developing countries. By improving access to scholarly literature from diverse fields of science and technology, ARDI seeks to:

- reinforce the capacity of developing countries to participate in the global knowledge economy; and
- support researchers in developing countries in creating and developing new solutions to technical challenges faced on a local and global level.

Share

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Databases Search: Identical for Journals, Books, Reference Sources and Free Resources

- Returning to the Unified Content Portal, click on **Content** menu.
- Note the options for Journals, Books, Reference Sources, Databases, Free Collections, Publishers, Recent Resources and Subject.
- Click on **Databases** - to access all the R4L resources in this category.

The screenshot shows the ARDI website interface. The browser address bar displays 'login.research4life.org/tacsg1ardi_research4life_org/'. The ARDI logo is at the top left, with the tagline 'Research for Innovation'. A navigation menu at the top right includes 'Content' and 'Help'. The 'Content' dropdown menu is open, listing 'Journals', 'Books', 'Reference Sources', 'Databases', 'Free Collections', 'Publishers', 'Recent Resources', and 'Subjects'. The 'Databases' option is highlighted with a blue bar. A red box surrounds the 'Content' menu, and red arrows point from the text in the adjacent list to the 'Content' and 'Databases' options. Below the navigation, a banner image shows a group of people in a meeting, with the text 'Welcome to ARDI' overlaid. A search bar is visible with the text 'information Technology' and 'Search function provided by Summon'. Below the banner, there is an 'About ARDI' section and a 'Share' button. The footer contains a cookie notice and the 'research4life' logo.

Databases Search continued

- All the R4L databases are listed in alphabetical order – a total of 43.
- Note that you can apply the **Collection, Publishers, Language** and **Subject** filters to the Databases listing.
- See the **Access Key** – in this case, all resources have the Green 'P' **Title Provided** symbol.
- The **Summon** search tool can be activated - by clicking on

The screenshot displays the ARDI (Research for Innovation) Databases search results page. The page features a search bar, a list of databases, and various filters. A red box highlights the 'Content Type' filter, which is set to 'Database' (13 results). Another red box highlights the 'Access Key' legend, which shows 'P' for 'Titles Provided', 'OA' for 'Open Access Content', 'F' for 'Free Content', and '!' for 'No Access Provided'. A red arrow points from the text 'by clicking on' in the list to a magnifying glass icon in the top right corner of the page.

Content Type	Count
Database	(13)

Publisher	Count
Lens, The	(3)
CABI Publishing	(1)
Elsevier	(1)
Google Scholar	(1)
IFIS Publishing	(1)

Database	Access Key
CAB Abstracts	P
CiteSeerX	F
Dimensions	P
Directory of Open Access Journals Search	F

Journals Search

- From the Content menu, the **Journals** collection has been opened. Using the filters, Computer Science (subject) with a total of 117 titles.
- Note the various options in the left column. Remember to de-active the filters by clicking on the **X**.
- Click on title **Advances in Multimedia** to link to the Directory of open access Journals.

The screenshot displays the ARDI (Research for Innovation) website interface. A red box highlights the 'Content' menu on the left, with 'Journals' selected. Another red box highlights the search results for 'Advances in Multimedia | Hindawi Limited'. A red arrow points from the 'Advances in Multimedia' title in the search results to the corresponding entry in the 'Journals' list on the left.

Content ▾ **Collect**

- Journals
- Books
- Reference Sources
- Databases
- Free Collections
- Publishers
- Recent Resources
- Subjects

ARDI
Research for Innovation

Content ▾ Help EN ▾ 🔍 👤 ☰

<input type="checkbox"/> Zoology, Animal Bio...		
<input type="checkbox"/> Soil Sciences	(70)	F Advances in Multimedia Hindawi Limited
<input type="checkbox"/> Physics	(66)	Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
<input type="checkbox"/> Toxicology	(60)	Coverage: 2007 - current issue
<input type="checkbox"/> Genetics	(58)	ISSN: 16875680
<input type="checkbox"/> Forestry	(58)	E-ISSN: 16875699
<input type="checkbox"/> Microbiology	(56)	Journal
<input type="checkbox"/> Geography	(53)	F Anale: Seria Informatică Mirton Publishing House, Timisoara
<input type="checkbox"/> Civil engineering	(52)	Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
<input type="checkbox"/> Natural Resources	(50)	Coverage: 2003 - current issue
<input type="checkbox"/> Pharmacy and Pharma...	(49)	ISSN: 15837165
<input type="checkbox"/> Pollution and Environ...	(45)	E-ISSN: 20657471
<input type="checkbox"/> Physiology	(42)	Journal
<input type="checkbox"/> Zoological Sciences	(42)	P Applied Artificial Intelligence
<input type="checkbox"/> Ecology and Wildlife Co...	(40)	Information Provider: Taylor & Francis
<input type="checkbox"/> Biotechnology	(40)	Coverage: v. 11:01 (1997) - current issue
<input type="checkbox"/> Chemical technology	(39)	ISSN: 08839514
		E-ISSN: 10876545

login.research4life.org/tacsgr1ardj_research4life_org/content/publishers/86 We use cookies to track usage and preferences. [I Understand](#) [+ More](#)

Journals Search continued

- The Articles and issues of the **Advances in Multimedia** in the Wiley Online Library are been displayed.
- Click on the article you interested in
- Please note the process for opening Books is identical.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/6048. The page is titled "Articles" and features two tabs: "Most Recent" (selected) and "Most Cited".

The first article listed is a Research Article with Open Access, titled "Classification of Gastrointestinal Diseases Using Hybrid Recurrent Vision Transformers With Wavelet Transform". The authors are Biniyam Mulugeta Abuhayi, Yohannes Agegnehu Bezabh, Aleka Melese Ayalew, and Miraf Alemayehu Lakew. It was first published on 28 September 2024. Links for Abstract, Full text, PDF, and References are provided.

The second article is also a Research Article with Open Access, titled "Image Super-Resolution Reconstruction Based on the Lightweight Hybrid Attention Network". The authors are Chu Yuezhong, Wang Kang, Zhang Xuefeng, and Liu Heng. It was first published on 20 September 2024. Links for Abstract, Full text, PDF, and References are provided.

On the right side of the page, there is an advertisement for Wiley with the text "How is AI changing the way we find and use information? Read this article to find out more." and a "Learn More" button. Below the advertisement, there is a "Related Titles" section with two book covers: "International Journal of Intelligent Systems" and "Applied".

Databases, Reference Sources and Free Collections, Subjects

- In the Content drop down menu, note the **Reference Sources, Databases** and **Free Collections , Subjects** listings.
- Also available are Interdisciplinary resources such as Research4Life/ Google Scholar, Dimensions and The Lens.

- Reference Source (98)
- Database (41)
- Free Collection (24)

Browse by Subject continued

- Opened is the **Civil Engineering** subject listing.
- Note that the filters (Collection, Content Type, etc.,) can be applied.
- The **Access Key** will note if the material is available at your institution.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the ARDI (Research for Innovation) website. The page is titled "Civil engineering" and features a search bar, a "Content Type" filter, and a "Publication date (books only)" filter. The "Content Type" filter shows "Book" (1196) and "Journal" (59). The "Publication date" filter has dropdown menus for "Month" and "Year". The "Access Key" legend is visible on the right side, indicating "Titles Provided", "Open Access Content", "Free Content", and "No Access Provided". The page also displays a list of books, including "21 European Symposium on Computer Aided Process Engineering" and "3D Art Essentials".

ARDI
Research for Innovation

Home / Civil engineering

Civil engineering

Search within Civil engineer

Content Type

Book (1196)

Journal (59)

Publication date (books only)

Month Year

To

Month Year

21 European Symposium on Computer Aided Process Engineering

Editor(s): E.N. Pistikopoulos, M.C. Georgiadis, A.C. Kokossis

Information Provider: Elsevier

E-ISBN: 9780444538956

Publication Date: 2011

Book

3D Art Essentials

Author(s): Ami Chopine

Information Provider: Elsevier

E-ISBN: 9780240814711

Publication Date: 2011

Book

Access Key

Titles Provided

Open Access Content

Free Content

No Access Provided

research4life

Academic and professional content for the developing world

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Hamburger Menu – additional tools

- Displayed is the Hamburger Menu – accessed from the initial Unified Content Portal page.
- Key additional tools are:
 - Search content
 - Personal Sign-in
- The subsequent slides are an overview of these two features.
- The **Search Content** tool searches the R4L journal and book titles plus authors but not the text; go to Summon for keyword searching.

Search Content – initial page features

- From the Hamburger menu, the **Search Content** page is displayed
- **Boolean logic, fields and Sort by options** are available.
- Note the limited # fields – **Publication Type, Author Name** and **DOI, ISSN or ISBM #** plus **All Fields**.
- The **Search Content** tool searches the journal or book titles available in Research4Life.

The screenshot displays the ARDI Search Content page. The search criteria 'hospitality' and 'tourism' are entered in the search bar, with 'AND' selected as the boolean operator. A red box highlights this search input area. Below the search bar, the 'Sort Results By' dropdown menu is set to 'Relevance', also highlighted with a red box. The page features a navigation bar with 'Content', 'Help', and 'EN' options. On the right, an 'Access Key' section lists content types: 'Titles Provided', 'Open Access Content', 'Free Content', and 'No Access Provided'. The Research4Life logo and tagline 'Academic and professional content for the developing world' are visible at the bottom right. A cookie notice is present at the very bottom of the page.

Topic search & results (e.g. Hospitality and Tourism)

- Type **public** and **health** with **All Fields** and sort results by **Newest First**
- Figure in the right shows the Search results and they are bolded in **yellow**.
- This search produced **252 results** – 1st four listed are 3 Journals and 1 publisher; books included.

Search Content

Enter one or more search criteria below. Boolean AND, OR and NOT are supported (e.g. health AND environment). Use quotation marks (") to find an exact phrase (e.g. "international law"). Use asterisks to match partial words in fields (e.g. agricultur*).

hospitality in
AND tourism in
+
Publication Title
All fields
Search

SEARCH BETWEEN THESE DATES
(BOOKS ONLY):

From to

SORT RESULTS BY:

Relevance

Search

home / Search Results

RESULTS: 1 - 10 of 10 for (contains 'hospitality') AND (All Fields excluding Full Text contains 'tourism')

Modify this search Next action Sort By: Relevance

R4L Portals - Search Results | ARDI: Access to Browse by Subject | Research4Life

login.research4life.org/tacmgr1ardi_research4life_org/search?value1=hospitality&option1=dterms_title&operator2=AND&value...

hospitality 0/11

ARDI
Research for Innovation

Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Coverage: 2020 - current issue
E-ISSN: 26873737
Journal

Book (7)
Journal (3)

Publication date (books only)
Month Year
To Month Year
Apply

Subject
Other Miscellaneous S... (7)
Home Economics (5)
Environmental Economics (1)
Geography, Population (1)
Development Studies (1)

African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure | AfricaJournals
Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Coverage: 2014 - current issue
E-ISSN: 2223814x
Journal

Tourism and Hospitality International Journal | Instituto Superior de Ciências Educativas (ISCE)
Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Coverage: 2013 - current issue
E-ISSN: 21830800
Journal

Entrepreneurship in the Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure Industries
Author(s): Alison Morrison, Mike Rimmington and Claire Williams
Information Provider: Elsevier
E-ISSN: 9780750640978
Publication Date: 1

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Academic and professional content for the developing world

Find out more

- Visit the training portal
- Sign up for the Research4Life MOOC and webinars
- Watch our videos on Youtube
- Video: New Research4Life Portal | Getting started

New Research4Life
RESEARCH4LIFE
NEW PORTAL
Watch on YouTube

Searching across Research4Life using Summon

- **Summon** is known as a 'Google-like' search engine.
- It allows users to **refine keyword searches** by content type, publication date, discipline, subject terms & language.
- Summon search results are mapped to the material that the publishers grant access to in a specific country & are linked to the full text.

Country Offer

To check the content that publishers have granted access to in a specific country and institution type,

- Open the **Hamburger Menu**.
- Click on **Reports**.
- Then click on **Country Offer**.

Country Offer continued

Displayed is the **Country Offer Page**. From the drop-down menu;

- Select a country e.g., **Rwanda**
- Select an institutional category e.g., **University, Faculty, College**
- Click on **Find**

Note the code used for the subsequent alphabetical list of Research4Life publishers that are granting access.

For Bhutan, the total access #s are 57209 books, 10614 journals, 26 reference sources and 15 databases

research4life

Content ▾ Collections ▾ Help EN ▾ 🔍 👤 ☰

Content offered by information providers to institution categories within countries, areas and territories. Information providers listed below are offering their content to the selected choices.

Select a country, area or territory
Rwanda ▾

Select institution category
University / Faculty / College ▾

Find

- Content is Open Access or freely available to all the world
- ★ Offer available beginning in the next calendar year
- ✕ Offer not available after the end of the current calendar year
- ✕ Offer available to non-paying institutions (relevant to Group B countries only)

Full Access: 71056 Book(s) 10022 Journal(s) 52 Reference Source(s) 12 Database(s)
203 Result(s)

Access to Medicine Foundation (1 Reference Source(s))

Access Key

- P Titles Provided
- OA Open Access Content
- F Free Content
- ! No Access Provided

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Find out more

- Visit the [training portal](#)
- Sign up for the Research4Life [MOOC](#) and [webinars](#)
- Watch our videos on [Youtube](#)
- Video: [New Research4Life Portal | Getting started](#)

Addleton Academic Publishers (15 Journal(s)) We use cookies to track usage and preferences. [I Understand](#)

Open, download a pdf and export a citation - access to IEEE (via Hamburger Menu/Search Content)

- The Lancet with **Publication Type** search results
- **438results** – click on the 1st listing

Search Content

Enter one or more search criteria below. Boolean AND, OR and NOT are supported (e.g. health AND environment). Use quotation marks (" ") to find an exact phrase (e.g. "international law"). Use asterisks to match partial words in fields (e.g. agricultur*).

ieeee in All fields

AND xplore in All fields

[+](#) [Search](#)

login.research4life.org/tacsgr1portal_research4life_org/search?value1=ieeee+&option1=fulltext&operator2=AND&value2=&option2=...

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Content Collections Help EN

Home / Search Results

RESULTS: 1 - 20 of 438 for (All Fields excluding Full Text contains 'ieeee')

Modify this search Next action Sort By: Relevance Access Key

Collection

- ARDI (352)
- AGORA (18)
- Hinari (7)
- OARE (6)
- GOALI (1)

Content Type

- Book (409)
- Journal (29)

IEEE Open Journal of Power Electronics | IEEE
Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Coverage: 2020 - current issue
E-ISSN: 26441314
Journal

IEEE Open Journal of Industry Applications | IEEE
Information Provider: Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
Coverage: 2020 - current issue
E-ISSN: 26441241
Journal

IEEE Journal on Exploratory Solid-State Computational Devices and Circuits | IEEE

Titles Provided
Open Access Content
Free Content
No Access Provided

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Open, download continued

- Via IEEE Xplore, the current you can see the computing with p-Bits: Devices, Architectures, and Algorithms has been opened.
- Follow the instructions in the subsequent slides.
- Note the link to Download PDFs.

The screenshot shows the IEEE Xplore website interface. The browser address bar displays the URL: `ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10068500`. The page title is "A Full-Stack View of Probabilistic Computing With p-Bits: Devices, Architectures, and Algorithms", which is highlighted with a red rectangular box. Below the title, the publisher is listed as "IEEE". There are buttons for "Cite This" and "PDF". The authors listed are Shuvro Chowdhury, Andrea Grimaldi, Navid Anjum Aadit, Shaila Niazi, Masoud Mohseni, and Shun Kanai. At the bottom left, there are statistics: "23 Cites in Papers" and "5395 Full Text Views". On the right side, there is a promotional banner for "Try out IEEE's Experimental AI-Based Search" with a "Try it Now!" button. The page also includes navigation links like "Browse", "My Settings", "Help", and "Institutional Sign In".

Summary

- This lesson focused on access to Research4Life collections ' resources by the Unified or AGORA or ARDI Content Portals.
- It explored how to browse/search by Content, Collections, Databases and Journals or search for the content across all collections.
- The lesson also covered additional resources that are available via the Databases, Reference sources and Free collections listings.
- Also reviewed is how to identify what the publishers have granted access to in a specific country/type of institution via the Content offered by publishers to institutions within countries, areas and territories page.
- Several additional resources from the Content Portal's help page and R4L training portal are summarized.

Additional Resources – Portal **Help** page

Content ▾ Collections ▾ **Help**

Content ▾ Collections ▾ |

Home / Research4Life help

Research4Life help

Find out more about Research4Life and how to contact us on the following links:

[Tips for using the new content portal](#)

[Contact Us](#)

[About Research4Life](#)

[FAQ](#)

[Access](#)

Home / Tips for using the new content portal

Tips for using the new content portal

Logging in

To login, click on the person icon at the top of the page:

You will be taken to the login page where you can enter your institution credentials as per the old portals

After logging in, you will be returned to the homepage, and the person icon will have changed to the profile icon:

Personal Sign-in

After logging in with your institution credentials you will now have the ability to create a personal profile on the portal, either by clicking on the 'Register/Sign-in as a personal user' link in the profile dropdown, or from the 'Personal Sign-in' option in the menu

Registering as a personal user allows you to save searches, create search alerts and set up a favourites list (site content searches only, does not apply to Summon searches).

When you are also signed in as a personal user, the profile icon dropdown will display your credentials and a link to 'My Profile' where you can access your personal profile.

Browsing Site Content

From the 'Content' menu option, you can browse by Journals, Books, Reference Sources, Databases and Free Collections (or by Collection from the 'Collections' menu option). When browsing using these options, there are various filters that you can use to refine your results, these are at the side of the page when using a desktop/laptop computer, or can be accessed via the blue 'Filter' button when using a mobile device.

From the 'Content' menu option, you can also choose to browse by Publishers, where you can filter alphabetically, or by Subjects, where you can page through the results.

The 'Recent Resources' menu option takes you to a page that displays content added in the last 30 days.

Searching With Summon

The new portals have Summon search functionality as per the old portals. Summon searches can be submitted from the homepage via the large search box within the image or by using the 'ADVANCED SEARCH' link under the search box.

Additional Resources – Research4Life Training Portal

[Home](#) / [Training](#)

Training

Access Research4Life training resources on the following links:

[Training Portal](#): find resources for librarians and researchers

[Getting Started](#): an overview of the partnership and its programmes

[MOOC](#): sign up to this online course get the most out of Research4Life

[Webinars](#): sign up to the latest webinars and find video recordings

[Training Presentations](#): up to date presentations about Research4Life and scholarly communications in general

[Resources for Librarians](#): resources specifically developed for information specialists

[Author Skills](#): readings and activities to help understand the scientific publishing process

[Partner Resources](#): free resources from related organisations and publishers

From the Hamburger Menu, users can access the **Research4Life Training Portal** numerous topical pages including **Training Presentations**